

Kinetics of Mn^{2+} catalysed oxidation of cyclic ketones by lead tetraacetate

A. K. Sambasiva Rao, B. Syama Sundar* and P. S. Radhakrishnamurti

Department of Chemistry, Nagarjuna University, Nagarjunanagar-522 510, India

E-mail : profbsyamsundar@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 14 February 2005, accepted 6 May 2005

Kinetics of oxidation of a few cyclic ketones – cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone, cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone by lead tetraacetate in acetic acid medium with perchloric acid catalysed by Mn^{2+} has been investigated. Reactions are uniformly zero-order in oxidant. The dependence on substrate is fractional with cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone and cycloheptanone. The dependence on substrate is unity with cyclooctanone. The dependence on Mn^{2+} is unity with cyclopentanone, zero-order with cyclohexanone and cycloheptanone where as it is fractional with cyclooctanone. Dependence on H^+ is fractional in the range studied. With cyclooctanone, rate tends to become zero on H^+ at higher concentrations of H^+ . The results have been analysed on the basis of conformations of these cyclic ketones. Cyclohexanone kinetically reacts faster. The order of reactivity is cyclohexanone > cyclooctanone > cycloheptanone ~ cyclopentanone

Kinetics of oxidation of cyclic ketones has been well studied by a number workers¹. The present investigation deals with the oxidation of a few cyclic ketones by lead tetraacetate (LTA) catalysed by Mn^{2+} in acetic acid medium.

Results and discussion

Reactions have been studied in 100% acetic acid at varying concentrations of perchloric acid mixtures in the presence of $MnCl_2$ as catalyst using LTA as oxidant.

Cyclopentanone system :

Effect of [LTA] : The reactions have been found to be of zero-order in the concentration range studied. Zero-order dependence on LTA becomes clear from an examination of time vs percentage plots, which are linear. k_0 values are constant in each run till about 75% of reaction. k_0 values remained constant at varying concentrations of LTA confirming zero-order nature of the reaction on LTA. The kinetic data is given in Table 1.

Effect of [substrate], $[MnCl_2]$ and $[H^+]$: The rate constants are recorded at varying concentrations of substrate, $MnCl_2$ and H^+ in Table 1. Dependence on the substrate is fractional as $\log k_0$ vs $\log [s]$ plot yields a fractional slope in cyclopentanone. A plot of $\log k_0$ vs $\log [MnCl_2]$ yielded a unit slope indicating a first-order dependence on $MnCl_2$ in cyclopentanone. The reaction rates increase with increase in concentrations of H^+ . The plots of $\log k_0$ vs $\log [H^+]$ are linear with a fractional slope indicating fractional depen-

dence on acidity. As the system is almost non-aqueous it was considered worthwhile to use H_0 values which does not lead to any major change of acidity dependence.

Effect of addition of water to the system on kinetic rate : Added water decreases the kinetic rate. The kinetic data is given in Table 1. It appears that the effect of water in the system is much different from that in the case of uncatalysed reaction. Probably there is no exchange of acetate by water molecules in the present system due to the presence of $MnCl_2$. An inorganic ion like Mn^{2+} may be competing for the water molecules, thus not making them available for exchange of acetate in the solvation sphere.

The reaction rate increases with the increase in temperature $\log k_0$ vs $1/T$ plot is linear. The thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 2. These parameters are of the right order of magnitude for bimolecular reactions.

Cyclohexanone, cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone systems :

As observed with cyclopentanone the dependence on oxidant is zero in all the cases. The dependence on substrate is fractional with cyclohexanone and cycloheptanone. Where as with cyclooctanone the dependence on substrate is one. The dependence on Mn^{2+} is fractional with cyclooctanone, where as it is zero-order with cyclohexanone and cycloheptanone. The dependence on H^+ is fractional with cyclohexanone, cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone.

Table 1. General experimental conditions

[LTA] = 0.0009 M, [Substrate] = 5×10^3 M, $[H^+] = 0.08$ M, AcOH-H₂O = 95%-5%, $[MnCl_2] = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ M, temp. = 50°C

System	Variation of LTA $\times 10^3 M$	Variation of Rate of substrate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$		Variation of Rate of $[H^+] \times 10^2 M \text{ min}^{-1}$		Variation of Rate of acetic acid (%) $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$		Variation of Rate of temp. ($^{\circ}C$) $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$		Variation of Rate of $MnCl_2 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$		Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$
		Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$	Rate $k_0 \times 10^6 M \text{ min}^{-1}$		
Cyclopentanone	0.1080	1.10	0.25	1.10	0.2	1.50	95	4.08	40	1.10	5	4.08
	0.2432	1.60	0.50	4.08	0.4	2.10	90	3.69	45	2.75	25	29.00
	0.3363	1.90	1.00	5.46	0.8	2.80			50	4.08	100	76.00
	0.4623	1.50	2.00	8.57	2.0	1.968						
	0.7500	1.38			6.0	3.939						
Cyclohexanone	0.10	40.00	0.125	1.483	0.01	7.50	95	4.00	40	17.45	5	40.00
	0.22	33.70	0.25	25.00	0.02	12.71	90	2.16	45	24.00	25	34.00
	0.49	35.17	0.50	40.00	0.04	17.20			50	40.00	100	39.80
			1.00	76.00	0.06	20.60					250	47.55
					0.08	40.00						
Cycloheptanone	0.20	4.8	0.2	2.08	0.01	2.03	95	4.0	45	1.30	5	4.0
	0.43	4.8	0.5	4.00	0.02	2.30	90	2.4	50	2.58	25	4.0
	0.68	4.1	1.25	6.50	0.06	2.73			55	4.00	100	4.1
Cyclooctanone	0.13	20.18	0.25	5.40	0.2	5.5	95	18.00	40	7.318	5	18.0
	0.19	18.18	0.50	18.0	1.0	12.0	90	11.36	45	12.4	40	21.5
	0.82	18.00	1.25	65.0	2.0	18.0			50	18.0	100	35.0
			2.00	92.6	8.0	18.0					200	40.0

But with cyclooctanone at higher concentration of H^+ the order is zero on H^+ .

Structural influences :

The order of reactivity is cyclohexanone > cyclooctanone > cycloheptanone ~ cyclopentanone.

Before discussing the conformational influences it is pertinent to comment up on the factors that lead to enol formation and its stability.

Table 2. The thermodynamic parameters

Substrate	ΔE kcal/mole	ΔH kcal/mole	ΔS e.s.u.	$\log_{10} A$
Cyclopentanone	22.50	21.87	-15.34	9.82
Cyclohexanone	18.00	17.37	7.80	-24.61
Cycloheptanone	22.50	21.87	-15.34	9.82
Cyclooctanone	19.06	18.43	8.17	-22.99

The enolisation of ketone depends up on two steps. (i) Equilibrium protonation of carbonyl groups. (ii) Deprotonation at α -carbon of the conjugate acid.

It is clear from the rates that cyclohexanone reacts faster than all the medium sized ketones. The order observed is cyclohexanone > cyclooctanone > cycloheptanone ~ cyclopentanone.

The higher reactivity of cyclohexanone calls for explanation. It is quite possible that the terminal hydrogen of the nearly strain less puckered residue $(CH_2)_4$ in cyclohexanone fulfills the stereo chemical requirements for hyper conjugation with the cyclic C=C group better than does the terminal hydrogen of the nearly, flat residue $(CH_2)_4$ in cyclopentanone. The order observed shows that the even numbered ketones react much faster in comparison with the odd numbered ketones. It is interesting to recall the similar differences between the spectra of even and odd numbered ketones.

For even numbered ring ketones, the spectrum changes suddenly at the melting point, while in the case of rest of the temperature range only slightly changes. For odd numbered ketones, the spectrum also changes, not at the melting point but at transition point which lies lower than the melting point. The change in spectrum may be interpreted as the possible disappearance of one or more conformations at the given point.

It is generally presumed that the most favoured conformation of cycloheptanone is the twist chair form.

This is responsible for the lowest rate observed in the oxidation process. Latest investigation shows that the cyclooctanone exists in the crown form though the spectral data is consistent with the chair form².

Cyclooctanone has its carbonyl stretching frequency at 1701 cm⁻¹. The lowering of the carbonyl frequency has been attributed to *trans* angular hydrogen bonding which is possible in the chair form. The differential reactivity between cyclooctanone and cyclopentanone is due to the crown form in the former and chair form in the latter. The results are quite consistent with the recent studies³ on the determination of the enol contents of the cyclic alkanones, where it has been observed that the enol content alters with the ring size.

Alternatively, if it is a keto form then the sequence of reactions may be as follows.

It is presumed that LTA functions as two electron oxidant leading to products in fast step.

An analysis of activation energy of the four substrates shows that the order of reactivity observed is cyclohexanone > cyclooctanone > cycloheptanone ~ cyclopentanone which is in tune with the experimental activation energies.

Rate law and mechanism :

In the present reaction under consideration the mechanism clearly envisages a transition from sp² carbon to sp³ carbon. In such transition the medium sized ring ketones react slowly and the reactivity of cyclohexanone is the highest as observed in the reaction. The conversion of sp² carbon to sp³ carbon leads to an increase in strain in medium sized ketones and hence they react slow. Such slowness of medium sized ring ketones and higher reactivity of cyclohexanone has also been found in the semicarbazide cyclic ketone reactions, in the reduction of cyclic ketones

by boron hydride and in the reactions of cyclic ketones by HCN.

In the present investigation the cyclic ketones have been subjected to oxidation by LTA under catalysed conditions with MnCl₂. It appears that in uncatalysed process, the keto form is a preferred system under acidic condition. But when the catalyst like MnCl₂ is used the following steps take place.

Initially ketone forms a conjugate acid with H⁺ ion. The conjugate acid complexes with Mn²⁺ in an equilibrium fashion. This complex breaks down to yield enol in a rate determining step. The enol is subsequently cleaved to form products.

The rate law and rate equations are as follows :

$$\begin{aligned}
 S + H^+ &\xrightleftharpoons{K} SH^+ \\
 SH^+ + Mn^{2+} &\xrightleftharpoons{K_1} \text{Complex [C]} \\
 \text{Complex} &\xrightleftharpoons{k} \text{Enol} \\
 \text{Enol} + \text{oxidant} &\xrightarrow{\text{fast}} \text{Products} \\
 \text{Rate} &= k [\text{Complex}] \\
 &= kK_1 [SH^+][Mn^{2+}] \\
 &= kK_1K[S][H^+][Mn^{2+}] \\
 &= \frac{kKK_1[S]_T[H^+][Mn^{2+}]}{\{1 + k[H^+]\}\{1 + k_1[Mn^{2+}]\}} \\
 &= \frac{kKK_1[S]_T[H^+][Mn^{2+}]_T}{\{1 + k[H^+]\}\{1 + k_1[Mn^{2+}]\}\{1 + kk_1[S][H^+]\}} \\
 &= \frac{kKK_1[S]_T[H^+][Mn^{2+}]_T}{\{1 + k_1[Mn^{2+}]\}\{1 + k[H^+]\}\{1 + kk_1[S][H^+]\}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Experimental

All the chemicals used are of analytical grade. The kinetics has been followed by iodometry.

5.0 ml aliquots from the reaction mixture and also from the blank were withdrawn at various intervals and added to 10 ml of 5% KI and excess of sodium acetate. The liberated iodine was titrated against the standardized thiosulphate solution. All the experiments were performed in duplicate and the results are reproducible with in ±5% error.

References

- (a) R. P. Bell and M. Spiro, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 429; (b) R. P. Bell and K. Yater, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 227, 2285; (c) R. P. Bell and G. G. Dewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 902; (d) S. P. Mushram, A. Sharma and A. K. Bose, *Bulletin dela Academic polonaise Desciences chimiques*, 1974, 889; (e) *Ann. Soc. Sci. Bruxelles Ser.*, 1975, 189, 567; (f) P. S. Radhakrishnamurti, N. K. Rath and D. K. Mahapatra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 207; (g) J.

Rao *et al.* : Kinetics of Mn^{2+} catalysed oxidation of cyclic ketones by lead tetraacetate

- P. Gurthrie, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**, 240, 797, 1177; (h) J. Hine, J. C. Kaufmann and M. S. Cholad, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 4590; (i) J. P. Gurthrie and Cossari, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1986, **64**, 2470, 2477; (j) G. D. Dlingeski, G. Blotny and R. N. Pollack, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 1019.
2. Leonard, Milligan and Brown, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 4075.
3. (a) Hendrikson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4537; (b) 1962, **84**, 3355; (c) *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 1387.